

80.26; H, 7.29; N, 11.91. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2$ requires: C, 80.67; H, 7.56; N, 11.77%.

ν_{max}^{KBr} 1575, 1465, 1370, 813 cm^{-1} , N.M.R. signals at δ 1.11 (6H, s, two $-CH_3$), δ 2.08 (3H, s, CH_3 on $-C=N$), δ 2.75 (2H, d, $J=2Hz$), δ 7.08 to 7.75 (7H, m, Ar-H).

Biological Data

Although 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(*p*-anilino)-2-pyrazoline (V) has ulcerogenic properties, it also shows good anti-inflammatory action. All the reported compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity against the following microorganisms: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhosa*, by agar plate technique⁷. Sulphonamides 4 (Table 1) and 6 (Table 2) as well as the 3-nitrophthalimide 9 (Table 2) showed total inhibition whereas sulphonamide 1 (Table 1) showed moderate inhibition⁸.

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Co-ordination complexes of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl/diethyl thiocarbamides

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CO-ORDINATION complexes of metal ions and parent and substituted aryl/alkylthiocarbamides have been reported earlier¹⁻⁴. N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl/diethyl thiocarbamides (I) which have an additional site in their structure for complex formation with metal ions, however, do not appear to have been investigated earlier.

Interaction of certain metal ions *viz.*, Cu^{++} , Co^{++} and Ni^{++} and N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl and diethyl thiocarbamides leading to neutral coloured com-

plexes forms the subject matter of this communication.

It has now been observed that when an aqueous solution of cupric sulphate (0.05M) is added to an alcoholic solution of N-benzoyl-N'-dimethylthiocarbamide (0.1M) at pH 6, a dark green complex, m.p. 205° is formed and can be isolated. On analysis and determination of its composition through complexometric titration by conductometry, the structure IIa was assigned to this complex. This structure is also supported on the basis of its infrared spectrum, where the presence of $\nu(C-S)$ at 727 cm^{-1} and $\nu(Cu-O)^5$ at 535 cm^{-1} bands have been observed. The absence of $-NH$ and $C=O$ stretching frequencies in the infrared spectrum further supported it.

where $R = R' =$ methyl/ethyl.

- where (a) $R = R' =$ methyl and $M =$ copper(II)
 (b) $R = R' =$ ethyl and $M =$ copper(II)
 (c) $R = R' =$ methyl and $M =$ cobalt(II)
 (d) $R = R' =$ ethyl and $M =$ cobalt(II)
 (e) $R = R' =$ methyl and $M =$ nickel(II)
 (f) $R = R' =$ ethyl and $M =$ nickel(II).

The proposed structure II for the complex is in full agreement with structural features of the thiocarbamide in which the hydrogen at position N is likely to contribute more towards enolic ($C-OH$) than thioenolic ($C-SH$) form for the co-valent bond formation in the complex because of the presence of phenyl group at the carbon of the carbonyl group.

When the interaction of Copper (II) was extended to N-benzoyl-N'-diethylthiocarbamide the related complex IIb was obtained. This structure is also supported by the presence of $\nu(C-S)$ at 720 cm^{-1} and $Cu-O$ at 535 cm^{-1} bands and absence of $-NH$ and $C=O$ bands in its infrared spectrum.

Cobalt(II) sulphate and Nickel(II) sulphate and N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- and diethyl thiocarbamides also afforded the related cobalt(II), IIc and II d and nickel(II), IIe and II f complexes. The infrared spectra of all these complexes also indicated

the presence of $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (727 cm^{-1} in IIc, 725 cm^{-1} in IIId, 727 cm^{-1} in IIe and IIIf) and absence of $-\text{NH}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bands. However, in these cases, the complexation reaction was found to occur at pH 9.

Electronic spectra of all the above complexes have been determined in visible region and their ν_{max} have been recorded in Table.

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TABLE
ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF Cu^{++} , Co^{++} AND Ni^{++} WITH N-BENZOYL-N'-DIMETHYL/DIETHYL THIOCARBAMIDES

S. No.	Metal ion	Name of thiocarbamide & m.p.	Composition of complex	Colour & m.p. of complex	Analytical Data						Wave number ν_{max} cm^{-1}	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
					Found %			Required %				
					N	S	M	N	S	M		
1	Cu^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- 138°	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Green 205°	11.80	13.25	13.20	11.74	13.42	13.31	18020	1.93
2	Cu^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-diethyl- 88°	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Green 115°	10.57	12.02	12.22	10.50	12.00	11.91	17930	1.84
3	Co^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- 138°	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Bluish Green 155°	11.65	13.35	12.15	11.79	13.47	12.42	16400	2.84
4	Co^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-diethyl- 88°	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Green 70°	10.35	11.72	10.91	10.58	12.10	11.15	16400	2.25
5	Ni^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- 138°	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Pale Pink 282°	11.50	13.10	12.21	11.79	13.47	12.42	19610	Diamagnetic
6	Ni^{++}	N-benzoyl-N'-diethyl- 88°	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$	Pale Pink 140°	10.49	11.82	11.37	10.58	12.10	11.15	19420	Diamagnetic

The complexes of Copper(II) and Cobalt(II) have been found to be paramagnetic. The complexes of Ni(II) have been observed to be diamagnetic. The magnetic moments of these complexes have been recorded in Table.

Experimental

The metallic salts used in the present studies were of A.R. grade. The required N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl/diethyl thiocarbamides have been prepared according to the earlier described procedure^{6,7}, i.e., by the interaction of benzoyl isothiocyanate and appropriate dialkylamine.

Nitrogen and sulphur estimations of the complexes have been done by Kjeldahl and Messenger method respectively. Composition of the complexes has been determined by conductometric method. Estimation of the metal ion in the complexes has been carried out by the conventional methods⁸. Infrared spectra of the complexes have been recorded employing Carl-Zeiss IR Spectrophotometer, Model UR-10.

Electronic spectra of the complexes have been recorded employing SPEKOL spectrophotometer and solutions were prepared in benzene/chloroform. The magnetic measurements were made at room temperature by the Gouy's method using MnO_2 as the magnetic standard.

Colour, m.p., analytical data etc., of the complexes have been recorded in the Table.

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Synthesis of a few Substituted -3-mercapto-s-triazolo (3, 4-b) benzothiazoles

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CHARLES *et al.*¹ synthesised certain derivatives of 3-mercapto-s-triazolo (3,4-b) benzothiazoles and reported their plant protection activity. Reactions of the 2-hydrazino benzothiazolo with carbon disulphide provided a convenient synthesis² of the above compounds. The 3-mercapto-s-triazolo (3,4-b)